

Reverse human factors – Why we adapt to processes and objects that are counter-intuitive and detrimental to human health and comfort

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Abstract Human Factors in Industrial Design has primarily focused on the development of ergonomic and user-friendly products that are shaped to fit human behaviour and human dimensions. In contrast, this paper focuses on how human beings are impacted by using the products that humans have designed. It demonstrates how products with apparently poor and inadequate Human Factor qualities develop and change our behaviour. The paper shows that through this process and these changes, we develop new ideas and new ways of perceiving ourselves in concert with our interaction with the product (“Reverse Human Factors”). Iconic consumer electronics and a number of other products are studied from this perspective. The case studies of Reverse Human Factors point to certain generic traits that should be recognized as drivers of innovation.

Keywords *Human factor, Innovation, Consumer electronics*

Introduction

Henry Dreyfuss (1904–72) is considered the founding father of Human Factors in Industrial Design. His work focused on how we can shape the physical world to make life easier and more comfortable for human beings. Dreyfuss’ work can be seen in the context of the twentieth century social design movement which sought to liberate housewives by tailoring kitchen design to time and motion studies of household actions. This was a reaction against the constrictive styles of the late nineteenth century in architecture and design. Dreyfuss’ ideas played a central role in the development of a modern American design culture acknowledged throughout the world in the 1950s, 60s and 70s for the easy and comfortable use it allowed. However, Dreyfuss’ achievements were based on the premise that human behaviour and levels of comfort could be observed empirically and were of a given nature. In that sense, Dreyfuss and the design traditions based on his ideas focus little on how products also shape us. Conditions and design objects have changed significantly since the 1970s, yet Dreyfuss’ *oeuvre* still sets the standard both for how classic industrial design human factors are taught and how they are implemented in industrial design practice. This paper is an inquiry into how and why these Dreyfuss standards, are now being tacitly challenged by a parallel approach, in which discomfort, inconvenience and even health risks are accepted in design for everyday use: Reverse Human Factors.

Method

The analysis consists of three 3 case studies.

The first two case studies focus on consumer electronics. The canon of ‘Good Human Factor’ qualities derived from Dreyfuss is compared with observations made by user experience (UX) researchers in industry on how people use smartphones and remote controls. This information is combined with marketing statistics and sales statistics for smartphones vs. traditional phones and statistics for touch-based screens in general. Ergonomic and medical perspectives are also included, as well as the authors’ experience from discussions on practice at the R&D centre of a major consumer electronics manufacturer.

These findings are put into perspective in the third case study and by a survey among students of industrial design.

The third case study is literature-based in the field of behavioural studies. It proposes a generic setting for the idea of ‘reverse human factors’ and the general phenomenon of user ability to adapt to poor human factors in the Dreyfuss sense.

The student survey was produced during an educational challenge presented to students on an industrial design programme at a North American University. They were asked to make individual presentations on everyday objects that they like to use but that also provoke discomfort and frustration. This small exercise was carried out as a spot check of current ‘reverse human factor’ trends.

Figure 1. Examples of devices combining buttons with touch screen. Left: Bang & Olufsen: Beo6; right: Samsung: Ultra Touch phone.

Case 1: Combined remote controls – an interim stage

The following observations concern a remote control device that combines buttons with touch screen functions. It can be perceived as an interim design between the traditional button interface and the full launch of the new touch screen technology. The method in the UX analysis was to observe a wide range of users focusing on the following questions: *Which of the two different interfaces (touch vs. buttons) did the users prefer? What differences were seen in different age groups? and What other factors had an impact?*

Users did not perceive the combination of touch screen and buttons as an advantage. Shifting from one type of interface to another made the device less convenient. This interim solution, bridging between button and touch screen technology was not preferred. Users preferred to adapt to the poor ergonomics of the touch screen interface, because of the additional functions associated with smart phones and the ability to manage large amounts of content data.

Users across various age groups preferred the touch screen interface. With regard to ‘other factors’, affordability proved to be important for all users.

Devices combining buttons with touch screens were a temporary phenomenon used until consumers became fully ‘educated’ in using the touch screen interface. Although it might be thought of as combining the best of both worlds – the good human factor quality from the buttons and the widening of functions from the touch screen – having two parallel interfaces was not experienced as a good solution.

Figure 2. US smartphone use in 2015. Using the internet equals the traditional telephone call functions. Source: (Smith, 2015).

Case 2: Touch screens in smartphones and laptops

In Case 2, we compared the canon of ‘Good Human Factor’ qualities derived from Dreyfuss with observations of the use of the glass touch screen of the smartphone. We also looked at statistics on how people use the smartphone, sales statistics of smartphones vs. traditional phones, and statistics of touch-based screens in general.

Touching small, detailed areas on a glass plate does not live up to traditional good Human Factor qualities or ergonomic values. Buttons better match human ergonomics and match the dimensions and tangible aspect of the fingertips. The use of a glass plate touch interface significantly increases the chances of developing strain and arthritis in fingers and hands (Kim, 2012), (Franklin, 2012), (Esra, 2015).

However, the multiple new smartphone functions motivate the user to invest the hard work in adapting

The mobile market is converting to smartphones

Figure 3. The mobile phone market is converting to smartphones. Sales of “touch-based” smartphones are rising in all markets compared with “non-smart” phones (Arthur 2015).

to tapping on a glass plate. In general, it is the smartphone that “educates” most people to use a touch-based interface.

In contrast to the smartphone situation, users of laptops already have all the functionalities of the smartphone. Introducing touch screens on laptops would mean users losing good human factors without having the motivation of gaining new functions. This explains why the introduction of touch screens in the laptop realm has not developed as much as expected (Buxton, 2010).

Affordability is another strong impacting factor. Sales of “touch-based” smartphones in different size (Salil, 2015) are rising in all markets compared with “non

smart” phones (Figure 3). Most of the rising sales of displays are for smartphone-related products like tablets and other consumer electronics. One explanation for this is the synergy coming from the fact that when prices drop, sales rise, and when sales rise, prices drop. The price typically depends on the market volume of the specific display size. Another reason for the fall in prices is the fact that manufacturing button-based interfaces is more expensive because they involve mechanical solutions, unlike touch-based interfaces. The discussion in the laptop industry on whether it makes sense to turn away from keyboards should be viewed in this light. In terms of human factors and ergonomics, consumers might well lose out in this development.

Figure 4. Global shipment forecast for touch screen displays from 2012–16. Source: (Statista, 2015)..

Figure 5. In general, it is the smartphone that “educates” most people in using touch-based interfaces. Tapping a glass plate does not live up to traditional good Human Factors or ergonomics.

Case 3: The bicycle – rewarded by broadening of perspective

A US Toy Safety Commission study of 4–6-year-old children learning to ride bicycles inquired into how this skill relates to and affects the child’s development (Mace, 2008). The study confirmed that children develop their motor skills, balance, and understanding of the physical environment as they learn to use the bicycle. The children’s enhanced motor skills and balance also impact their other activities.

In relation to the development of the child’s self-confidence, it is significant that the child starts to understand the environment in a different way. When a child rides a bike, he/she literally sees the environment from a different perspective and develops a new understanding of distances.

From the perspective of this paper, the child’s ability to adapt to riding a bicycle derives from the motivation of broadening his/her perspective on the world. Learning to ride a bike is troublesome and involves moments of poor human factors, but children are willing to struggle to obtain the benefits of moving faster than running. It is a fact that no bike fits a child perfectly and cycling can be quite dangerous.

The US Toy Safety Commission study observed that as soon as a child had adapted to one bike, he/she preferred that specific one. This was not because it was the best from a human-factor perspective, but because that was the one to which he or she had adapted when learning to ride a bike. The reward for adapting to poor human factors (the broadening of perspective) had already been obtained and there was no motivation for adapting to new bicycles.

Student survey

Through student assignments on an Industrial Design course at a North American university, a picture was drawn of the scope of everyday objects that students like in spite of their experience of discomfort when using them. Medical and sports equipment was not part of the exercise, which focused solely on everyday articles. The students were also asked how their experience impacts on how they feel about these

Figure 6. The child adapts to the bike and learns how to ride it.

products. The choices of products/objects were individual and not coordinated among the students.

The survey was based on four courses with 20–45 participants in each. The three main groups of products (defined by the number of times students chose them for their individual reports) were:

1. Consumer electronics. Many examples similar to those mentioned above related to touch screen technology.
2. Fashion / Clothing. There were many examples of reverse human factors. High-heel shoes were often chosen by students as examples of poor human factors. For adults, these are connected with a learning curve that is, in principle, similar to that of the child learning to ride a bicycle. The motivation is to ‘feel in charge’ by adding to one’s height. Again, the perspective of the world is broadened as with the bike. (There is also a complex issue of cultural notions about beauty ideals involved, which makes it questionable whether high-heel shoes are ‘everyday objects’).
3. Websites: Students often mentioned specific website interfaces that were difficult to manage, but that had such interesting content that the students learned how to navigate. In many cases the driving factor was about finding products for an attractive price and saving money.

Often products with a lasting good experience started off being difficult to learn to use. The more people learned how to use the product, the more they started to appreciate it. This situation could be identified as one of Reverse Human Factors.

Conclusions

It is difficult but important to see what is just a small adaptation to the use of the product and what is actually the product ‘educating’ us to use it and helping us to develop new behaviour. The happiness and sense of achievement in experiencing access to

Figure 7. From the beginning of time, human beings have learned to adapt to poor human factors.

new functions and new perspectives on the world is the motivation for struggling to adjust to and learning to use products with 'poor' human factor quality.

Interim phenomena occur between old and new ways of using items. However, parallel or combined ways of using a product were not perceived as a convenience.

The Laptop PC example shows that users are not willing to adapt to poor human factors if no new perspective is achieved by this. However, more economical ways of producing an interface is a motivating factor for the manufacturing industry when they try out solutions with poor human-factor quality. More research is needed into the degree to which consumers are willing to adapt to poor human factors if the product is more affordable.

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